

GoNEXUS modalities for accessing datasets

September 2025, UPV
WP1

GoNEXUS has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101003722.

www.gonexus.eu

Global and continental model codes

The following links provide access to the source code of the global and continental models for which it is available (PCR-GLOBWB₂, Lisflood-EPIC, CAPRI and GLOBIO). PRIMES, PROMETHEUS and GEM-E₃ are not open-source, in line with the rules established by its developer, E3M. For all models, a link to the model documentation is also provided.

PCR-GLOBWB₂

Model code

https://github.com/UU-Hydro/PCR-GLOBWB_model

Model documentation

<https://pcrglobwb.readthedocs.io/en/latest/#>

Lisflood-EPIC

Model code

<https://github.com/ec-jrc/lisflood-code>

Model documentation

<https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/>

PRIMES

Model documentation

<https://e3modelling.com/modelling-tools/primes/>

Also description on the EC portal for modeling tools: [Modelling tools for EU analysis - European Commission](#)

PROMETHEUS

Model documentation

<https://e3modelling.com/modelling-tools/prometheus/>

GEM-E₃

Model documentation

<https://e3modelling.com/modelling-tools/gem-e3/>

CAPRI

Model executables

https://www.capri-model.org/dokuwiki_help/doku.php?id=getting_started_with_capri#download_the_current_release

Model documentation

https://www.capri-model.org/dokuwiki_help/doku.php

GLOBIO

Model code

<https://github.com/GLOBIO4/GlobioModelPublic/wiki>

Model documentation

<https://www.globio.info/>

Links to GoNEXUS datasets

GoNEXUS datasets can be divided into two main types: those freely accessible according to the provisions set in this document, and those that are not. In case that the latter are publicly available in the future, the links provided would either be valid and grant free access, or would be re-directed to the proper ones.

Freely accessible data

This data refers to the open datasets linked to GoNEXUS publications. Consequently, the data is organised by publication.

- Topwatch modelling results - GoNEXUS Zambezi case study: <https://zenodo.org/records/16095105>
- GoNEXUS SEF application: Andalusia practical case study: <https://zenodo.org/records/7544931>
- Data in support of "Declining cost of renewables and climate change curb the need for African hydropower expansion": <https://zenodo.org/records/7931050>
- Data and code in support of "Floating PV Reduces Risks of Hydro-Dominated Energy Development in Africa": <https://zenodo.org/records/10576226>
- Data supporting the findings of Keijzer et al. (2024) Threats of dams to the persistence of the world's freshwater fishes. Global Change Biology: https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Data_supporting_the_findings_of_Keijzer_et_al_2023_Threats_of_dams_to_the_persistence_of_the_world_s_freshwater_fishes_Global_Change_Biology_/24981228
- Data and code in support of "Rethinking energy planning to mitigate environmental and climatic impacts of future African hydropower": <https://zenodo.org/records/8360437>

Data with restricted access

These datasets are available upon request to the contact for queries included in the tables at the end of this document, under the access modalities set out in the next section. Currently, their access is restricted to UU Yoda users with access to the GoNEXUS Yoda folder. In case that in the future, following the provisions set out by the GoNEXUS Consortium Agreement and the GoNEXUS Exploitation Strategy (D8.8), this data is openly shared, the links indicated below would be valid, or an updated version of this document, including the proper links, would be uploaded into Zenodo.

The following datasets are organised by type. Tier 1 data refers to results obtained by the models before their interconnection, while Tier 2 corresponds to the results achieved by the interconnected model runs. Details on each dataset are provided in the next section, including contact for queries.

- Scenario data
 - Climate scenarios
 - Global and continental scale: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/1_Scenario_data/1_Climate_scenarios/ISIMIP/
 - River basin scale: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/1_Scenario_data/1_Climate_scenarios/River_Basins/
 - Land use and socioeconomic scenarios: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/1_Scenario_data/2_Landuse_and_socioeconomic_scenarios/

- Model data
 - Global model runs
 - PCR-GLOBWB2:
 - Tier 1: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2 Baseline tier 1 model runs/1 Global models/1 PCR GLOBWB/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2%20Baseline%20tier%201%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/1%20PCR%20GLOBWB/)
 - Tier 2: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3 Baseline tier 2 model runs/1 Global models/1 PCR GLOBWB/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3%20Baseline%20tier%202%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/1%20PCR%20GLOBWB/)
 - CAPRI:
 - Tier 1: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2 Baseline tier 1 model runs/1 Global models/2 CAPRI global runs/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2%20Baseline%20tier%201%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/2%20CAPRI%20global%20runs/)
 - Tier 2: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3 Baseline tier 2 model runs/1 Global models/2 CAPRI global runs/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3%20Baseline%20tier%202%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/2%20CAPRI%20global%20runs/)
 - PROMETHEUS:
 - Tier 1: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2 Baseline tier 1 model runs/1 Global models/3 PROMETHEUS/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2%20Baseline%20tier%201%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/3%20PROMETHEUS/)
 - Tier 2: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3 Baseline tier 2 model runs/1 Global models/3 PROMETHEUS/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3%20Baseline%20tier%202%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/3%20PROMETHEUS/)
 - GEM-E3:
 - Tier 1: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2 Baseline tier 1 model runs/1 Global models/4 GEM E3/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2%20Baseline%20tier%201%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/4%20GEM%20E3/)
 - Tier 2: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3 Baseline tier 2 model runs/1 Global models/4 GEM E3/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3%20Baseline%20tier%202%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/4%20GEM%20E3/)
 - GLOBIO:
 - Tier 1: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/1_Global_models/5_GLOBIO/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2%20Baseline%20tier%201%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/5%20GLOBIO/)
 - Tier 2: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3 Baseline tier 2 model runs/1 Global models/5 GLOBIO/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3%20Baseline%20tier%202%20model%20runs/1%20Global%20models/5%20GLOBIO/)
 - Continental model runs
 - LISFLOOD-EPIC:
 - Tier 1: <https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ftp/private/zyWXm7fga/cSqZ5potYSKnyZt5/>
 - Tier 2: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3 Baseline tier 2 model runs/2 Continental models/1 LISFLOOD EPIC/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3%20Baseline%20tier%202%20model%20runs/2%20Continental%20models/1%20LISFLOOD%20EPIC/)
 - PRIMES:
 - Tier 1: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2 Baseline tier 1 model runs/2 Continental models/2 PRIMES/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2%20Baseline%20tier%201%20model%20runs/2%20Continental%20models/2%20PRIMES/)
 - Tier 2: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3 Baseline tier 2 model runs/2 Continental models/2 PRIMES/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3%20Baseline%20tier%202%20model%20runs/2%20Continental%20models/2%20PRIMES/)
 - CAPRI:
 - Tier 1: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2 Baseline tier 1 model runs/2 Continental models/3 CAPRI EU runs/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2%20Baseline%20tier%201%20model%20runs/2%20Continental%20models/3%20CAPRI%20EU%20runs/)
 - Tier 2: [https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3 Baseline tier 2 model runs/2 Continental models/3 CAPRI EU runs/](https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/3%20Baseline%20tier%202%20model%20runs/2%20Continental%20models/3%20CAPRI%20EU%20runs/)
 - Case study model runs
 - Zambezi

- High resolution model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/1_High_resolution_models/1_Zambezi/
- Many-objective model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/2_Many_objective_models/1_Zambezi/
- System dynamics model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/4_System_dynamics_models/3_Zambezi/
- Como
 - High resolution model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/1_High_resolution_models/2_Como/
 - Many-objective model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/2_Many_objective_models/2_Como/
 - Behavioural model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/5_Behavioural_models/1_Como/
- Danube
 - Many-objective model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/2_Many_objective_models/3_Danube/
- Jucar
 - Many-objective model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/2_Many_objective_models/4_Jucar/
 - Hydro-economic model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/3_Hydroeconomic_models/1_Jucar/
 - System dynamics model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/4_System_dynamics_models/1_Jucar/
 - Behavioural model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/5_Behavioural_models/2_Jucar/
- Tagus-Segura
 - Hydro-economic model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/3_Hydroeconomic_models/2_Tagus_Segura/
 - System dynamics model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/4_System_dynamics_models/2_Tagus_Segura/
- Senegal
 - Hydro-economic model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/3_Hydroeconomic_models/3_Senegal/
 - Behavioural model: https://geo.data.uu.nl/research-gonexus-shared/2_Baseline_tier_1_model_runs/3_River_basin_models/5_Behavioural_models/3_Senegal/

Modalities of access

In general, the access to the GoNEXUS datasets shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions and upon written bilateral agreement between the owning Party (the party of the contact for queries) and whoever requests access (the receiving Party), or between the legal signatories of both.

For the avoidance of doubt, the decision on what are Fair and Reasonable conditions shall be at the absolute discretion of the owning Party. The following conditions are included as a general guideline of what is considered as Fair and Reasonable conditions at the date at which the document was produced.

In any case, proper acknowledgement to the GoNEXUS project and the European Union funding should be made, through the following (or very similar) statement: *"this research uses results from the GoNEXUS project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003722"*.

Access rights to Results for non-commercial research and teaching activities shall be granted on a royalty-free basis. In this case, the owning Party may:

- Request proper acknowledgement to its efforts in producing the datasets used.
- Request co-authorship of any dissemination activity that uses their datasets (e.g. research articles, books, book chapters, conference presentations).
- Request that any result obtained using the datasets shared will be subject to the same licensing as that used for the datasets shared (e.g. non-commercial, no-derivative).
- Request access to any result obtained using the datasets shared, under the same licensing conditions.

Commercial research activities are understood as any that will result in an economic return to the receiving Party in any of its forms, including but not limited to royalties, access fees, awards, contracts, grants, and tenders.

For commercial research activities, on top of the guidelines included for non-commercial research, the owning Party may:

- Request a share of any future royalties or access fees collected.
- Request a share of any award achieved.
- Request to be included as partner or beneficiary in any contract, grant or tender applied to.

Any share or partner budget from those referred above will be in line with the relevance of the dataset shared for the success of the product or service to be developed by the receiving Party.

Any Affiliated Entity of a GoNEXUS partner, or any other department, section, institute or body of any GoNEXUS entity other than the one involved in the project, requesting access rights to other GoNEXUS partner, should inform the main contact of the GoNEXUS team of its partner prior to requesting access rights.

The datasets will be shared in a non-exclusive way, with no time limit. The owning Party may retain the Intellectual Property Rights.

The owning Party must not be liable for any error, omission or any other issue concerning the datasets shared or its application.

No other service nor obligation apart from delivering the data in the format with which it was stored in UU Yoda may be assumed by the owning Party.

GoNEXUS Data Tables

Table 1: Data collected and post-processed

Do not include raw datasets (they should be referred to the original source)

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LAND USE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEXUS SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
isimip_adj-w5e5_CMIP6_MM_HISTORICAL	Multi-model mean	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rlds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	ISIMIP3 BASD	GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM-1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL	LUH2	historical	historical	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rlds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	global	daily	1971-2014	Global historical	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5	Daniel.e.peano@cmcc.it
isimip_adj-w5e5_CMIP6_MM_SSP126	Multi-model mean	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rlds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	ISIMIP3 BASD	GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM-1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL	LUH2	SSP1	RCP2.6	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rlds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	global	daily	2015-2100	Global, ssp126	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5	Daniel.e.peano@cmcc.it
isimip_adj-w5e5_CMIP6_MM_SSP370	Multi-model mean	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rlds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	ISIMIP3 BASD	GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM-1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL	LUH2	SSP3	RCP7.0	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rlds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	global	daily	2015-2100	Global, ssp370	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5	Daniel.e.peano@cmcc.it

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LAND USE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEX US SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
isimip_adj-w5e5_CMIP6_MM_SSP585	Multi-model mean	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	ISIMIP3 BASD	GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM-1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL	LUH2	SSP5	RCP8.5	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	global	daily	2015-2100	Global, ssp585	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5	Daniel.e.pearo@cmcc.it
day_MMM_ssp119	Multi-model mean	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	no	GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL	LUH2	SSP1	RCP1.9	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	global	daily	2015-2100	Global, ssp119	V1	netcdf	CMCC	no	Daniel.e.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to ERA5L_gfdl-esm4_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_historical	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	gfdl-esm4	LUH2	historical	historical	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	1979-2014	Local basin, historical	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to ERA5L_gfdl-esm4_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp126	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	gfdl-esm4	LUH2	SSP1	RCP2.6	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp126	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to ERA5L_gfdl-esm4_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp370	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	gfdl-esm4	LUH2	SSP3	RCP7.0	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp370	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to ERA5L_gfdl-esm4_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp585	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	gfdl-esm4	LUH2	SSP5	RCP8.5	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmx, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp585	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LAND USE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEX US SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
									basin, Zambesi basin								
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_ipsl-cm6a-lr_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_historical	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	lpsl-cm6a-lr	LUH2	historical	historical	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	1979-2014	Local basin, historical	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_ipsl-cm6a-lr_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp126	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	lpsl-cm6a-lr	LUH2	SSP1	RCP2.6	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp126	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_ipsl-cm6a-lr_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp370	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	lpsl-cm6a-lr	LUH2	SSP3	RCP7.0	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp370	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_ipsl-cm6a-lr_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp585	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	lpsl-cm6a-lr	LUH2	SSP5	RCP8.5	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp585	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Mpi-esm1-2-hr_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_historical	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Mpi-esm1-2-hr	LUH2	historical	historical	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	1979-2014	Local basin, historical	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Mpi-esm1-2-hr_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp126	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Mpi-esm1-2-hr	LUH2	SSP1	RCP2.6	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp126	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Mpi-esm1-2-hr_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp370	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Mpi-esm1-2-hr	LUH2	SSP3	RCP7.0	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin,	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp370	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LAND USE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEX US SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
									Zambesi basin								
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Mpi-esm1-2-hr_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp585	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Mpi-esm1-2-hr	LUH2	SSP5	RCP8.5	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp585	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Mri-esm2-o_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_historical	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Mri-esm2-o	LUH2	historical	historical	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	1979-2014	Local basin, historical	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Mri-esm2-o_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp126	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Mri-esm2-o	LUH2	SSP1	RCP2.6	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp126	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Mri-esm2-o_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp370	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Mri-esm2-o	LUH2	SSP3	RCP7.0	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Como, ssp370	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Mri-esm2-o_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_ssp585	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Mri-esm2-o	LUH2	SSP5	RCP8.5	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp585	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Ukesm1-o-ll_r1i1p1f1_w5e5_historical	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Ukesm1-o-ll	LUH2	historical	historical	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	1979-2014	Como, historical	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to_ER A5L_Ukesm1-o-ll_r1i1p1f2_w5e5_ssp126	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Ukesm1-o-ll	LUH2	SSP1	RCP2.6	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin,	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp126	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LAND USE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEX US SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
									Zambesi basin								
ISIMIP_downscaled_to ERA5L_Ukesm1-0-ll_r1i1p1f2_w5e5_ssp370	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Ukesm1-0-ll	LUH2	SSP3	RCP7.0	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp370	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
ISIMIP_downscaled_to ERA5L_Ukesm1-0-ll_r1i1p1f2_w5e5_ssp585	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	Ukesm1-0-ll	LUH2	SSP5	RCP8.5	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	2015-2100	Local basin, ssp585	V1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it
W5E5v2.o_downscaled_to ERA5L	Statistical downscaling, ISIMIP3BASD	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	ISIMIP3BASD	W5E5	/	historical	historical	Hurs, pr, ps, rlds, rsds, sfcWind, tas, tasmax, tasmin	Como Lake, Danube basin, Iberian peninsula, Senegal basin, Zambesi basin	daily	1981-2019	Local Basin, reanalysis	v1	netcdf	CMCC	W5E5, Era5-Land	Daniele.pearo@cmcc.it

Table 2: Data generated

Include only datasets further used in GoNEXUS (e.g. to build the evidence, or to analyse the performance of solutions)

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LANDUSE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEXUS SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
PCR_GLOBWB_nonrenewableAbstraction_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Non-renewable abstraction per water origin	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Non-renewable abstraction	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_renewableAbstraction_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Renewable abstraction per water origin	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Renewable abstraction	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_domestic_watergap_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Domestic water gap	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Domestic water gap	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_industry_watergap_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Industry water gap	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Industry water gap	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_irrigation_watergap_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Irrigation water gap	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Irrigation water gap	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_livestock_watergap_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Livestock water gap	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Livestock water gap	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LANDUSE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEXUS SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
																	r.vanbeek@uu.nl
PCR_GLOBWB_waters_tressindex_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Water Stress Index	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Water Stress Index	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_domestic_withdrawal_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Domestic withdrawal	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Domestic withdrawal	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_industry_withdrawal_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Industry withdrawal	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Industry withdrawal	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_irrigation_withdrawal_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Irrigation withdrawal	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Irrigation withdrawal	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
PCR_GLOBWB_livestock_withdrawal_output.nc	PCR-GLOBWB2	Livestock withdrawal	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	IMAGE	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Livestock withdrawal	Global	Daily (native); monthly and annual (averaged from daily data)	1990-2100	Historical SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1 Tier 2	Netcdf	UU	N/A	Marc Bierkens (m.f.p.bierkens@uu.nl), Rens van Beek (r.vanbeek@uu.nl)
CAPRI_Tier_1.csv	CAPRI	Total production Crop yield Feed use Food use Total land use Area harvested	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Total production Crop yield Feed use Food use Total land use Area harvested	Global EU	Annual (native), decadal (averaged from annual data)	2015-2050	SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1	CSV	UPM	N/A	Maria Blanco (maria.blanco@upm.es), Imen Arfa

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LANDUSE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEXUS SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
		Total use per sector Fertilisers N Total GHG emissions Total N2O emissions						Total use per sector Fertilisers N Total GHG emissions Total N2O emissions									imen.arfa@upm.es
CAPRI_Tier_2.csv	CAPRI	Total production Crop yield Feed use Food use Total land use Area harvested Total use per sector Fertilisers N Total GHG emissions Total N2O emissions	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Total production Crop yield Feed use Food use Total land use Area harvested Total use per sector Fertilisers N Total GHG emissions Total N2O emissions	Global EU	Annual (native), decadal (averaged from annual data)	2015-2050	SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 2	CSV	UPM	N/A	Maria Blanco maria.blanco@upm.es , Imen Arfa imen.arfa@upm.es
PROMETHEUS_Tier_1.xlsx	PROMETHEUS	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1 SSP3	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	Global	5-year	2015-2050	SSP1-2.6 (NetZero) SSP3-7.0 (Current pool)	Tier 1	XLSX	E3M	Emissions, costs and energy production per sector	Kristina Riepin kristina.govorukha@ricardo.com
PROMETHEUS_Tier_2.xlsx	PROMETHEUS	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1 SSP3	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	Global	5-year	2015-2050	SSP1-2.6 (NetZero) SSP3-7.0 (Current pool)	Tier 2	XLSX	E3M	Emissions, costs and energy production per sector	Kristina Riepin kristina.govorukha@ricardo.com
PRIMES_Tier_1.xlsx	PRIMES	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1 SSP3	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	EU	5-year	2015-2050	SSP1-2.6 (NetZero) SSP3-7.0 (Current pool)	Tier 1	XLSX	E3M	Emissions, costs and energy production per sector	Kristina Riepin kristina.govorukha@ricardo.com

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LANDUSE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEXUS SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
PRIMES_Tier_2.xlsx	PRIMES	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1 SSP3	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	EU	5-year	2015-2050	SSP1-2.6 (NetZero) SSP3-7.0 (Current pool)	Tier 2	XLSX	E3M	Emissions, costs and energy production per sector	Kristina Riepin (kristina.govorukha@ricardo.com)
GEM_Tier1_CurPol.xlsx	GEM_E3	GDP Household total expenditure House food expenditure	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP3	RCP 7.0	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	Global	5-year	2015-2100	SSP3-7.0	Tier 1	XLSX	E3M	N/A	Kristina Riepin (kristina.govorukha@ricardo.com)
GEM_Tier1_NetZero	GEM_E3	GDP Household total expenditure House food expenditure	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1	RCP 8.5	GDP Capital cost Carbon capture Energy production CO2 emissions Gross emissions Carbon price Energy price	Global	5-year	2015-2100	SSP1-2.6	Tier 2	XLSX	E3M	N/A	Kristina Riepin (kristina.govorukha@ricardo.com)
GLOBIO Tier 1	GLOBIO	PAF (potentially affected fraction of species) ESH (endangered species habitat)	N/A	Gfdl Hadgem Ipsl Miroc noresm	N/A	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	Historical RCP 2.6 RCP 4.5 RCP 6.0 RCP 8.5	PAF (potentially affected fraction of species) ESH (endangered species habitat)	Global	Monthly (native), averages for 2015 and 2031-2050	2015-2050	RCP 2.6 RCP 4.5 RCP 6.0 RCP 8.5	Tier 1	CSV	PBL	N/A	Aafke Schipper (aafke.schipper@pbl.nl)
LISFLOOD_EPIC Tier 1	LISFLOOD-EPIC	Discharge runoff groundwater storage	N/A	EC-EARTH - HIRHAM5 EC_EARTH - RACMO22E MPI-ESM-LR - CCL4-8-17	N/A	SSP2 SSP5	Historical RCP 4.5 RCP 8.5	Discharge runoff groundwater storage	EU	Daily	1979-2100	RCP 4.5 RCP 8.5	Tier 1	NetCDF	JRC	N/A	Berny Bisselink (berny.bisselink@ext.ec.europa.eu)
Zambezi Watercourse Pareto Solution Archive of Reservoir Operations with New Hydropower	Zambezi Watercourse Design Model	Streamflow; Reservoir Releases; Irrigation Diversions;	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Zambezi	Monthly	1986-2005	Historical	V1	.txt	POLIMI	N/A	Wyatt.Arnold@polimi.it; Andrea.Castelletti@polimi.it;

DATASET NAME	MODEL NAME	VARIABLE	BIAS CORRECTED	FORCING CLIMATE MODEL	FORCING LANDUSE MODEL	SSP SCENARIO	RCP SCENARIO	VARIABLE NAME	REGION	TIME STEP	PERIOD	GoNEXUS SCENARIO	VERSION	FORMAT	DATA PRODUCER	OBSERVATIONS	CONTACT FOR QUERIES
and Floating Solar Infrastructure		Reservoir Release Policies (RBF)															Matteo.Gluliani@polimi.it
Jucar River Basin baseline historical and future trajectories for CMIP6 scenarios	STIG-CROPROD	Reservoir storages and releases Groundwater storage and pumping Streamflows Supply and deficit to demands Crop yields Economic benefits in demands Hydropower production Hydropower benefits Fish habitat (WUA)	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Reservoir storages and releases Groundwater storage and pumping Streamflows Supply and deficit to demands Crop yields Economic benefits in demands Hydropower production Hydropower benefits Fish habitat (WUA)	Jucar River Basin	Annual (crop production and benefits), monthly (rest of variables)	1980-2070	SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1	XLSX	UPV	Forcing data from TETIS and AQUACROP available. Global forcing data from CAPRI and PRIMES available (see CAPRI-related records)	Hector Macian-Sorribes (hecmasor@upv.es)
Jucar River Basin future trajectories for CMIP6 scenarios including WEFE solutions	STIG-CROPROD	Reservoir storages and releases Groundwater storage and pumping Streamflows Supply and deficit to demands Crop yields Economic benefits in demands Hydropower production Hydropower benefits Fish habitat (WUA)	N/A	gfdl-esm4 ipsl-cm6a-lr mpi-esm1-2-hr mri-esm2-0a ukesm1-0-ll	N/A	SSP1 SSP3 SSP5	RCP 2.6 RCP 7.0 RCP 8.5	Reservoir storages and releases Groundwater storage and pumping Streamflows Supply and deficit to demands Crop yields Economic benefits in demands Hydropower production Hydropower benefits Fish habitat (WUA)	Jucar River Basin	Annual (crop production and benefits), monthly (rest of variables)	2016-2070	SSP1-2.6 SSP3-7.0 SSP5-8.5	Tier 1	XLSX	UPV	Forcing data from TETIS and AQUACROP available. Global forcing data from CAPRI and PRIMES available (see CAPRI-related records)	Hector Macian-Sorribes (hecmasor@upv.es)